

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 52

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 52

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 52:0 For the choir director. A †Maskil of David, °when Doeg the Edomite came and told Saul and said to him, “David has come to the house of Ahimelech.”</p>	<p>לְמִנְצַחַת מִשְׁכֵּיל לְדָוִד : Psa. 52:1</p>
<p>Psa. 52:1 Why do you ^aboast in evil, O mighty man? ^bThe ^clovingkindness of God <i>endures</i> all day long. ² Your tongue devises ^d“destruction, Like a ^esharp razor, “O worker of deceit. ³ You ^flove evil more than good, ^gFalsehood more than speaking what is right. ¹Selah. ⁴ You love all words that devour, O ^hdeceitful tongue.</p>	<p>Psa. 52:2 וַיִּגְדַּר לְשֹׂאוֹל וַיֹּאמֶר לוֹ בֵּן דָּוִד אֶל-בֵּית אַחִימֶלֶךְ : ³ מֵה- תִּתְהַלֵּל בְּרָעָה הַגִּבּוֹר תִּסְדֹּר אֵל כָּל-הַיּוֹם : ⁴ הַיּוֹת תִּתְחַשֵּׁב לְשׁוֹנֶה כְּתֹעַר מְלִפְטֵשׁ עֹשֶׂה רַמְיָה : ⁵ אֶתְהַבֶּה דָּע מִטּוֹב שֶׁקָּרַ אֶתְהַבֶּה צֶדֶק סָלַח : ⁶ אֶתְהַבֶּה כָּל-דְּבַר-יְדִי-כָּלֵעַ לְשׁוֹן מִרְמָה : ⁷ גַּם-אֵל וַתִּצְדָּק לִנְצַחַת יִחַתְתֶּךָ וַיִּסְתַּחֲמֶךָ מֵאֲהֵל וּשְׂרָשֶׁף מֵאֶרֶץ תִּיָּם סָלַח : ⁸ וַיִּרְאוּ צַדִּיקִים וַיִּירְאוּ וְעָלְיוּ יִשְׁחַקוּ : ⁹ הִנֵּה הַגִּבּוֹר לֹא יֵשִׁים אֱלֹהִים מִעֵינָיו וַיִּבְטַח בְּרַב עֲשָׂרוֹ יָעַז בְּתוֹתוֹ : ¹⁰ וַאֲנִי אֶכְנִית רַעַנָן בְּבַיִת אֱלֹהִים בְּטַחְתִּי בְּחֶסֶד-אֱלֹהִים עוֹלָם וָעֶד : ¹¹ אֹדְךָ לְעוֹלָם כִּי עֲשִׂיתָ וַאֲקוּנָה שִׁמְךָ כִּי-טוֹב נִגְדַר תִּסְיַדֶּיךָ :</p>
<p>Psa. 52:5 ¹But God will break you down forever; He will snatch you up and ^atear you away from <i>your</i> tent, And ^buproot you from the ^cland of the living. Selah. ⁶ The righteous will ^dsee and fear, And will ^elaugh at him, <i>saying</i>, ⁷ “Behold, the man who would not make God his refuge, But ^ftrusted in the abundance of his riches <i>And ^gwas strong in ^hhis evil desire.”</i></p>	<p>וַיִּסְתַּחֲמֶךָ מֵאֲהֵל וּשְׂרָשֶׁף מֵאֶרֶץ תִּיָּם סָלַח : ⁸ וַיִּרְאוּ צַדִּיקִים וַיִּירְאוּ וְעָלְיוּ יִשְׁחַקוּ : ⁹ הִנֵּה הַגִּבּוֹר לֹא יֵשִׁים אֱלֹהִים מִעֵינָיו וַיִּבְטַח בְּרַב עֲשָׂרוֹ יָעַז בְּתוֹתוֹ : ¹⁰ וַאֲנִי אֶכְנִית רַעַנָן בְּבַיִת אֱלֹהִים בְּטַחְתִּי בְּחֶסֶד-אֱלֹהִים עוֹלָם וָעֶד : ¹¹ אֹדְךָ לְעוֹלָם כִּי עֲשִׂיתָ וַאֲקוּנָה שִׁמְךָ כִּי-טוֹב נִגְדַר תִּסְיַדֶּיךָ :</p>
<p>Psa. 52:8 But as for me, I am like a ^agreen olive tree in the house of God; I ^btrust in the lovingkindness of God forever and ever.</p>	<p>וַאֲנִי אֶכְנִית רַעַנָן בְּבַיִת אֱלֹהִים בְּטַחְתִּי בְּחֶסֶד-אֱלֹהִים עוֹלָם וָעֶד : ¹¹ אֹדְךָ לְעוֹלָם כִּי עֲשִׂיתָ וַאֲקוּנָה שִׁמְךָ כִּי-טוֹב נִגְדַר תִּסְיַדֶּיךָ :</p>

<p>⁹ I will ^agive You thanks forever, because You have done <i>it</i>, And I will wait on Your name, ^bfor <i>it is</i> good, in the presence of Your godly ones.</p>	
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References

<p>Psalm 52:0 Possibly <i>Contemplative</i>, or <i>Didactic</i>, or <i>Skillful Psalm</i> ¹1 Sam 22:9</p> <p>Psalm 52:1 ^aPs 94:4 ^bPs 52:8</p> <p>Psalm 52:2 ^aPs 5:9 ^bPs 57:4; 59:7 ^cPs 101:7</p> <p>Psalm 52:3 ¹<i>Selah</i> may mean: <i>Pause</i>, <i>Crescendo</i> or <i>Musical interlude</i> ^aPs 36:4 ^bPs 58:3; Jer 9:5</p> <p>Psalm 52:4 ^aPs 120:3</p> <p>Psalm 52:5 ¹Or <i>Also</i> ^aIs 22:18, 19 ^bProv 2:22 ^cPs 27:13</p> <p>Psalm 52:6 ^aPs 37:34; 40:3 ^bJob 22:19</p> <p>Psalm 52:7 ¹Or <i>his destruction</i> ^aPs 49:6 ^bPs 10:6</p>	<p>Psalm 52:8 ^aPs 92:12; 128:3; Jer 11:16 ^bPs 13:5</p>
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Targum

Psa. 52:1 For praise; for good teaching; composed by David.

Psa. 52:2 When Doeg the Edomite came and told Saul, and said to him, “David has come to the house of Ahimelech.” ³ How the mighty man will praise himself with a wicked tongue, to shed innocent blood; [but] the grace of God is all the day. ⁴ Your tongue will devise tumult in your heart, forming words of slander like a sharp knife. ⁵ You love evil more than good, lying more than speaking righteousness always. ⁶ You love all the words of destruction, the tongue of guile. ⁷ Also God will demolish you forever; he will shatter you and make you wander so that you cannot dwell in a tent; and he will uproot you from the land of the living forever. ⁸ And the righteous will see the punishment of the wicked, and they will be afraid in the presence of the LORD, and on his account they will laugh. ⁹ And they will say, “Behold, the man who did not make the word of the LORD his strength; he trusted in his riches; he was strong in his money.” ¹⁰ But I, like a luxuriant olive tree in the sanctuary of God, have trusted in the grace of God forever and ever. ¹¹ I will give thanks in your presence forever, for you have accomplished the vindication of my case; and I will await your name, for it is good, before your pious ones.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

This Psalm speaks to the most critical moral problem of David's day. The problem was spreading slander and the fabrication of evil tales to destroy rituals or people. David cites a situation in his life in which this occurred.

David was forced to feel like a beggar because of the jealous wrath of his father-in-law King Saul. During his flight, David was starving and unarmed. He traveled to the city of Nob, where the Tabernacle was located. He spoke with Achimelech, the priest who gave David bread and a sword. Achimelech thought that David was on a conquest for King Saul. Achimelech supplied David with what he needed.

At the same time, Doeg the Edomite, the head of the Sanhedrin, and Saul's closest advisor, went on a spiritual retreat. He went to Nob because the Tabernacle was there. He learned what Achimelech did and reported it to King Saul. He created the rumor that Achimelech was a conspirator against Saul. This incited Saul to condemn the entire city of Nob to death as rebels. Doeg carried out the sentence.

The Edomites and Hebrews were enemies at this time. Therefore, Doeg was a traitor to his people. He believed in the God of Israel and wanted to be a part of the Hebrew nation. Saul elevated him to a position of power that was reserved for men of Israel.

Superscript

David calls to the Sefirah Netzach for victory.

To the Sefirah Netzach and instruction of David, when Doeg the Edomite had come and told Saul, “David has come to the house of Achimelech.”

Verse one

How the mighty man will praise himself with a wicked tongue, to shed innocent blood; but the grace of God is all the day.

Verse two

How many times does a person think about the destructive power of speech? Words can hurt like a sharp razor. Doeg created slander that Achimelech assisted David to help David over through Saul. This slander was created by a misunderstanding of circumstances. Doeg wanted Achimelech removed as a priest in Nob, or he did not do his homework to learn why Achimelech assisted David. Today this can be seen when news reports and politicians jump to incorrect conclusions about an event. Facts must be checked and separated from fiction and emotions.

Your tongue devises destruction like a sharp razor, a worker of deceit.

Verse three

David said that Doeg could have discovered the facts when he was in Nob. Doeg could have come before Saul and pleaded David’s case. Instead, he created this slander against David and Achimelech. An entire town was destroyed because Doeg was angry with David.

Doeg loved evil more than good, falsehood rather than speaking righteousness. Meditate on this verse.

Verses four & five

David said that Doeg's acts against him and Achimelech showed that Doeg was a dangerous man. Doeg was a person who enjoyed using his words to bring disaster upon innocent people. Doeg represented peril to human happiness. The LORD will send such people away because of their evil influence on others.

But since you are a friend of all devouring words, of the tongue of deceit, God will also break you forever; He will send you away and remove you far from every tent and uproot you from the land of life. Meditate upon this verse.

Verses six & seven

The Torah could not protect Doeg because he was filled with evil and ungodly arrogance. Evil inclination can build up in a person that even the Torah, positive energy, cannot break through the klippot (the shell that forms around a person filled with evil and is a barrier that prevents goodness from entering the person).

The righteous will see it and be afraid, but they will laugh at him.

Behold the man who did not let God be the source of his strength. He trusted in the abundance of his wealth. Let him be strong, then, by means of what he has devised.

Verse eight

For David, he knew that he had inalienable rights in the House of the LORD. No person can deprive a person of the love of the LORD. Doeg placed his trust in his wealth and position in Saul's court. David put his faith in the mercy of the LORD.

But as for me, I am like the evergreen olive tree in the House of God. I trust in the mercy of God forever.

Verse nine

I will yet give You (God) thanks forever because you have done it, and I will wait upon Your name as it is good unto Your devoted ones.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach and instruction of David, when Doeg the Edomite had come and told Saul, “David has come to the house of Achimelech.”

How the mighty man will praise himself with a wicked tongue, to shed innocent blood; but the grace of God is all the day.

Your tongue devises destruction like a sharp razor, a worker of deceit.

Doeg loved evil more than good, falsehood rather than speaking righteousness.

Meditate on this verse.

But since you are a friend of all devouring words, of the tongue of deceit,

God will also break you forever; He will send you away and remove you far from every tent and uproot you from the land of life. Meditate upon this verse.

The righteous will see it and be afraid, but they will laugh at him.

Behold the man who did not let God be the source of his strength. He trusted in the abundance of his wealth. Let him be strong, then, by means of what he has devised.

But as for me, I am like the evergreen olive tree in the House of God. I trust in the mercy of God forever.

I will yet give You (God) thanks forever because you have done it, and I will wait upon Your name as it is good unto Your devoted ones.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

